

SEAMARK DELIVERABLE 3.1: DEVELOPMENT PLAN FOR PRODUCT SPECIFICATION

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Public summary of
confidential report

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Summary:

Oceanium biorefinery produces a range of food, nutrition and materials ingredients. Oceanium has registered OCEAN HEALTH® trademark for fibre and protein food ingredients and OCEAN ACTIVES® trademark for the fucoidan and beta-glucan bioactive ingredients.

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OCEAN ACTIVES® fucoidan has completed production development, product specification and regulatory approval for the US market (TRL 8). The product is undergoing further development during 2023 to substantiate health claims for both the nutraceutical and cosmeceutical markets. EFSA novel foods approval will be required for sale in the EU.

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OCEAN ACTIVES® beta-glucan has completed laboratory development and product specification (TRL 5). The product is undergoing production development, regulatory US GRAS preparation, and health claim substantiation during 2023 and 2024 (TRL 8).

Work Package / Task:

3 / T3.1 Process plant setup

Keywords:

algae, circular economy, ecosystem services

OCEAN HEALTH® fibre has completed production development and product specification and is in the final stages of regulatory approval for the US market (TRL 8). The product is undergoing further application development and will be evaluated for EU regulatory clearance during 2023.

Oceanium has filed a patent for four bio-based materials formulations (TRL 4) based on its kelp fibre product. These formulations are undergoing further development during 2023-2028 in order to match market specifications for application in apparel (textiles and shoes), printing, packaging, and coatings. These developments are being undertaken collaboratively with end user companies and will lead to development of further intellectual property for Oceanium.

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